

Low repetition load domain vs Creatine kinase Δ rel
 $r=0.258$, $p=0.0102$

Low repetition load domain vs Lactate Δ rel
 $r=-0.621$, $p<0.0001$

Low repetition load domain vs Cortisol Δ rel
 $r=-0.215$, $p=0.0321$

Moderate repetition load domain vs Creatine kinase Δ rel
 $r=0.409$, $p<0.0001$

Moderate repetition load domain vs Lactate Δ rel
 $r=0.582$, $p<0.0001$

Moderate repetition load domain vs Cortisol Δ rel
 $r=0.557$, $p<0.0001$

High repetition load domain vs Creatine kinase Δ rel
 $r=-0.102$, $p=0.3111$

High repetition load domain vs Lactate Δ rel
 $r=0.856$, $p<0.0001$

High repetition load domain vs Cortisol Δ rel
 $r=0.583$, $p<0.0001$

Total training load vs Creatine kinase Δ rel
 $r=0.475$, $p<0.0001$

Total training load vs Lactate Δ rel
 $r=0.434$, $p<0.0001$

Total training load vs Cortisol Δ rel
 $r=0.601$, $p<0.0001$

